

Entrepreneurial Pursuits Of Weavers In Low Resource Handloom Industry

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Abstract

Handloom weaving is an age old craft which is passed from one generation to another as a family legacy which makes it like family business but lack of proper management skills such entrepreneurial skills this profession is not getting its due recognition resulting in a situation where this art is almost on the verge of extinction. But the younger generation is not very keen to continue this family occupation due to lack of recognition, low wages, poor working conditions and difficulty in raw material procurement and selling of finished products. And also, they face stiff competition from power loom which can easily imitate the design and can make the same design in less time. Weavers need to be enabled to interpret designs and technical advancements, convert them into final product within stipulated time. The individual weavers work under master weavers. The master weavers often get an advantage by maintaining a low transaction cost and social capital. The entrepreneurial functioning in this sector is quite an interesting thing. Government also is working tirelessly in promoting this sector.

Keywords: Rural Enterprise, Handloom, Technology Adoption, Entrepreneur, Sustainable Fashion

1. Introduction

Handloom weaving is an age old craft which is passed from one generation to another as a family legacy which makes it like family business but lack of proper management skills such entrepreneurial skills this profession is not getting its due recognition resulting in a situation where this art is almost on the verge of extinction. But the younger generation is not very keen to continue this family occupation due to lack of recognition, low wages, poor working conditions and difficulty in raw material procurement and selling of finished products. And also, they face stiff competition from power loom which can easily imitate the design and can make the same design in less time. Weavers need to be enabled to interpret designs and technical advancements, convert them into final product within stipulated time. The individual weavers work under master weavers. The master weavers often get an advantage by maintaining a low transaction cost and social capital. The entrepreneurial functioning in this sector is quite an interesting thing. Government also is working tirelessly in promoting this sector.

2. Background Of The Study

It is a significant study as to understand the skilling process of a community, which is traditionally a community of weavers in the context of the fast-changing conditions of the market through a process of competition. Basically, the community is relying on only informal learning process. They have been in informal sector for a long period. But now they are organised through cooperative societies to save them from vulnerability. Both the governments

the centre and the state are taking earnest efforts to upgrade their skills to compete in the market for their survival and to enhance their income. Yet, they rely on mostly the informal learning and they continuously exert pressure on the government to get some relief. Government is insisting that they have to upgrade their skill

needed to the market and for which government is willing to support. Only a few are moving towards the formal training. Why they are not using this opportunity to enhance their skill to face the market, is a serious question to be pondered over. By analysing the issues of the weavers, the study is able to meaningfully give insights about their interest to become a entrepreneur. If weavers became entrepreneur there will not be down of handloom weaving and it leads to the sustainability of the handloom industry.

3.Statement Of The Problem

Business world is highly competitive for any sector and they have to face so many problems. The handloom weavers' societies are no exception to this Weavers co-operative societies are established with the objective of improving the economic conditions of the poor weavers. In this modern world of technological advancement, the societies face various problems in many fields like production, marketing and finance. The problems are Lack of Finance, Inadequate supply of yarn by Co-optex, Supply of inferior quality of yarn, Competition from master weavers and power loom owners, Lack of improvement in the modernisation of looms, Non- utilisation of multichannel marketing, Absence of innovative designs and combination of colours, Absence of timely decisions to cope up with the prevailing circumstances, due to economic conditions of the weavers, lack of utilization of support from the government and other sectors and Lack of competition among the weavers co-operative societies.

4.Need For Study

This project is based on the handloom weavers' entrepreneurial capabilities. From the survey we came to identify that now a days the number of handloom weaving has been decreased due to the development of technology. Handloom weaving is present mostly in rural areas and is ingeneral a family activity. However, it does no longer suggest that weavers are unbiased producers. Some handloom weavers work in cooperative societies where they are shareholders. The role of handloom weavers in the socio-political sector and the sector's annual contribution to the economy cannot be actually stated. These factors have hindered growth in the handloom sector and the growth in power looms, now supplying extra than 70% of Indian textiles, in step with textile ministry statistics, got here on the heels of a systematic destruction of the handloom

sector. The people who was involved in the handloom weaving was not much educated and they were under the poverty line. The people who involved in weaving have weaving as their full-time occupation and they don't get much orders. They don't prefer to expand their business because they don't have enough education and background even though they have a sufficient knowledge on the weaving sector. In the recent trends, handloom products rarely find a place in the textile sector but they still resist in the business because they involved in the weaving formore than two generations.

5.Research Questions:

- Would the handloom weavers be interested to take up individual business or would be interested to become retailer in future ?
- Can the weavers be motivated based on the requirements to start the business-like interest to market products, Own business if support given, to invest to start own business and sufficient contact to produce raw material?
- Test the significance of the correlation between knowledge on raw materials with that of production abilities and business inclination.
- To find the difference between the mean scores of the two groups (gender) is significant?
- To find whether there is any significant difference influencing entrepreneurial factors based on education qualification.
- Identify the major components contained in these many variables like Future interest to market products, own business if support given, retailer in future, distributor in future, design facilities in their area, willingness to start business and knowledge in type of yarn, to a few components.

6.Objectives Of The Study

1. To examine the socio – economic status of handloom weavers
2. To measure the technology adoption practices among the handloom weavers
3. To identify the major factors that determines the weaver’s willingness to start own business
4. To measure the awareness of various key activities in the handloom production value chain

7.Proposed Model

8.Scope Of The Study

The present study is confined to the silk, cotton, silk-cotton handloom weavers in South India and the weaving clusters are found in Alangombu, Sirumugai, Pollachi, Negamum and other clusters in South India. The descriptive research has attempted to study the socio-economic conditions of the handloom weavers, problems faced in adoption of technology and production, willingness to take up entrepreneurial pursuits, and marketing of handloom products. The study has reached to the handloom weavers spread in the entire district and the sample of handloom weavers were taken up for the direct interviews through two stage sampling process. The handloom products from this region are GI product Kovai Kora Silk Sarees, Soft Silk Sarees, Silk Sarees, Cotton Sarees, Dhotis and towels. Though the sample is limited to Coimbatore handloom weavers, it can be expanded to other handloom clusters.

9.Review Of Literature

Gunti Amaravathi, Dr. K. Bhavana Raj, (2019) examined Indian handloom sector – a glimpse that it is ancient, cultural heritage, traditional, decentralized, family-based, laborious, artistic skill and transfer of skills from one generation to another. In every stage of productionlike warping, dying, winding, weaving, etc., family members inputs labor. Weavers are mainly from the vulnerable and weaker sections of society, who generally weave for their livelihood. The diversity in India has been seen in the Indian handloom sector also, like in products, designs, weaving styles, usage of looms, employment status, economic position, etc., every state continuing their heritage and culture. In India, the handloom sector spread across the country and providing employment to nearly 43 lakhs and 28 lakhs households are depended on this sector.

Sushmitha Singh, Shashi Srivastava, (2018) examined the strategic management perspectivefor sustainable development in the handloom industry that how the cooperative weavers workunder the registered government cooperative institutions. Loom-less weavers do not have loom of their own and are employed under master weaver’s factory premises. They get the supply of

raw material (yarn) from master weavers and in turn wages are paid. Wages are decided on thebasis of the negotiating power of the weavers and intricacies of the designs. However, the negotiating power of weavers has drained substantially during the last decade as the industry is facing a downtrend. One more type of loom-less weavers are the ones who have been givena loom by master weavers and installed at their homes. The traders are the owners of the loomand weavers are paid the wages. The independent weavers are not under the wages system.

Sushmita Singh, Shashi Srivastava, (2018) examines external factors affecting Indian hand loom industry this sector has been part of the rich cultural heritage the country possess, as handloom has been associated with our culture since Mughal Period. Till date this sector has undergone various changes due to technological advancements, economic developments, government interventions and competition from mill weaved cloth. The sustainability of this sector is owed to the Government interventions and unmatched weaving skills of the artisans. In spite of the support from government, the weavers are facing a lot of issues like poor wages, poor working conditions & occupational health hazards. PESTLE analysis is an acronym for Political, economic, social, legal, environment factors.

K. Rari John, S. Kamini, (2015) examined dimensions of entrepreneurial behaviour of handloom weavers in thiruvananthapuram and kannur districts where entrepreneurial behaviour in its broadest sense has become more important in our society, where tasks increasingly require qualities. These entrepreneurial qualities enable individuals to cope with, and contribute to rapid changes in the society. A successful entrepreneur weaver needs some characteristics or dimensions of entrepreneurial behaviour. The dimensions like risk taking ability, achievement motivation, entrepreneurial motivation, management orientation, credit orientation, level of aspiration, innovativeness and self-confidence are some of the attributes behind the success of an entrepreneur.

K. Shanmuga Sundaram, M. Prakash, (2014) examined study on impact of cad / cam tools on production of punched cards by Indian silk saree designers for handloom industry the total export earnings of silk items for India in the year 2011-12 are US\$ 491.10 and also it is continuing to be US\$ 423.37 (Provisional) for the year 2012-13. This statistic shows the significance of silk fabrics in Indian economy. Most of this silk are used to produce sarees. India is also the largest consumer of silk in the world. The tradition of wearing silk sarees in marriages by the brides is followed in southern parts of India. Handloom forms a precious part of generational legacy and exemplifies the richness, which has been kept alive by skilled weavers and designers engaged in the age-old tradition of weaving. The designers with their

skilful blending of myths, faiths, symbols and imagery provide their fabric an appealing dynamism. Their strength lies in innovative designs, which cannot be replicated by the powerlooms. It is second only to agriculture sector in terms of providing employment in India. This sector contributes nearly 15% of the cloth production in the country. Nearly 95% of the world's hand-woven fabric comes from India.

Ruby Jain, Rachana Goswami, (2014) examined strategy for sustainable development of handloom industry where handloom industry is perhaps the most important one, among the hundreds of small scale and cottage arts and crafts that have survived in the present day in India. The present study concentrates on the awareness level and socio demographic profile of the handloom weavers of Jaipur district. The variables like housing, income, education, assets, child and mother mortality were analysed to derive the socio demographic status. The study reflected the overall low level of awareness among the weavers on various aspects of cooperative society and government programmes. The cooperative sector of handloom industry in Rajasthan state is operated and developed by Rajasthan Rajya Bunkar Sahakari, Sangh (RRBSS), which was established in 1957. The main objective of the organization was to provide raw materials to weavers, market the handloom product & form handloom co-operative societies in the state (Samarika, 2001). All these efforts are undertaken to promote the handloom industry & to strengthen the weaver.

Tirthankar roy, (2002) examined the acceptance of innovations in early twentieth-century Indian weaving in the standard narrative, Indian industrialization tends to be identified with the rise of mechanized factories. The adverse impact on Indian handlooms of competition with British power-loom cloth, aided by superior productivity and possibly by colonial policies, seems to illustrate that the gains and losses were unequally distributed. Industrialization in one part of the world imposed large uncompensated costs upon another. As if to undermine this view, at the close of the twentieth century, several hundred thousand handloom weavers survived in south Asia. In an alternative view, persistence of an archaic textile technology on such a scale suggests that the costs have been exaggerated, that industrialization can be of different kinds.

Suresh Bhagavatula, Tom Elfring d, Aad van Tilburg c, Gerhard G. van de Bun, (2010) examined how social and human capital influence opportunity recognition and resource mobilization in India's handloom industry small-scale firms in rural areas play an extremely

important role in the development of any country, and especially in developing countries. To understand entrepreneurs who operate in a low-technology industry, we rely on the network perspective on entrepreneurship. In addition to examining the direct effects, we also explore the possibilities of social capital mediating between human capital, on the one hand, and opportunity recognition and resource mobilization on the other.

Shaw Tanusree, (2015) examined a study of the present situation of the traditional handloom weavers of

Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India The Handloom is a traditional industry of India and it provides employment opportunities to millions of people in the rural and urban belts of our country. After industrialization, the handloom industry has been declined. Most of the problems faced by handloom industry are perpetual in nature and hence to sustain the cultural and economic importance of the industry the present study is an attempt to understand the various problems of Handloom Weavers of Varanasi in Uttar Pradesh. The problems are invention of new technology (power-loom), capitalist control, drop off in wages, increased price of yarn, and so on. The present study is descriptive in nature. The data have been collected through the in-depth interview, semi structured interview, case study and focused group discussion.

Rajiv H Peters, Dr. Shobhit Bajpai, (2017) examined the role and working of handloom sector in Chhattisgarh. The concentration of handloom industries in Northern, Southern and Central Regions of Chhattisgarh with reference to the number of weaving cooperative societies operated, number of active looms used and number of weavers employed. The study focused on the most and least handloom production units of Chhattisgarh. The study finds that Central Region of Chhattisgarh consists of maximum hand-loom units. This also explores that the increase in number of weaving cooperatives and active looms results in increased number of weavers which, later on increase in production of handloom products. Finally, it reveals that among all districts, Janjgir- Champa acquires maximum handloom production and their kosa/Tussar fabrics have made a mark in the domestic as well as the international market.

Parala Venkata Sree Vyshnavi, Suja S Nair, (2017), examined handloom sector in India explained that hand loom is a simple machine used for weaving. It is a manual operating system. Shedding is done by pressing the treadles pedal and picking and beating is done manually. In a wooden vertical-shaft looms, the heddles are fixed in place in the shaft. This loom is powered by hand. The warp threads pass alternately through a heddle, and through a space between the heddles (the shed), so that raising the shaft raises half the threads (those passing through the heddles), and lowering the shaft lowers the same threads—the threads passing through the spaces between the heddles remain in place [4]. Hand looms yield less production compared to

power loom. It can be operated at slow speed only compared to high speed of power looms. Initial investment is very low compared to power loom.

Anu Varghese, D M H Salim, (2015) examined about the handloom industry in Kerala: a study of the marketing issues examined the in the ongoing reforms era, particularly in the post-2000 period, there has been constant decline in the performance of the handloom industry in Kerala. Kerala's performance has been generally poorer than that of India as a whole. Both production and marketing declined a lot during the period. So, the state's export earnings from handlooms have been dwindling over the years. As already noted, economic reforms have had adverse impact on the handloom industry of Kerala which in turn is dominated by the co-operative sector (about 95 per cent). This decline is reflected in the official statistics of Hantex

– the apex cooperative society and Handveev – the apex promotional agency. Another major problem faced is lack of assistance from the government in the form of subsidies to purchase weaving accessories. The banks are not ready to pay loans to the handloom sectors. Some scheduled banks are giving loans by charging high rates of interest. The weavers were facing a stiff challenge from the power loom sector, though people like to purchase handloom material, there was no proper encouragement to them. Power loom goods are offered at cheaper rates and handloom products are not able to compete with them as we need better manpower. The power looms, by nature of their organization for production are able to offer products at a lower price. It is possible due to the difference in technology. Power loom production requires less number of laborers and less time. Most of the people prefer power loom products due to its low price which in turn affect the demand for the handloom product.

10. Research Methodology

Type of study: Descriptive research – To identify the weaver's willingness to become entrepreneur were the study explains about the characteristics of the weavers based on the data.

Population description: The population taken for the research is the handloom weavers.

Sample size: The researchers have taken a sample size of 150 handloom weavers; 66 % was the response rate and 100 responses were collected through direct interviews.

Sampling Frame: In the research study, out of 116 villages in the identified different weaving clusters, 7 villages were selected using purposive sampling method due to higher loom concentration in these areas in the first stage.

Source of data collection: Primary data is collected with the help of structured questionnaire from the handloom weavers of in district in India.

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Research design: Descriptive research design was adopted. It aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables. In our research we claim it as descriptive research because we investigate the weaver's weather, they have the interest to start their own business with the kind of facilities they have in their area, willingness to become an entrepreneur, contact and facilities they have in their area and interest to become distributor or retailer with the parametric analysis.

Sampling method: Handloom saree weavers list specializing in cotton, silk-cotton and silk yarns was sourced from The Centre for Weavers, Samathur. The list had 500 saree weavers list spread across seven villages in South India. In the second stage area sampling method was adopted to have a random representation of the handloom weavers from these villages.

Tools for data collection: The questionnaire was structured comprising of 26 questions starting from the questions in the basic demographic details like name, number of years in the business ending with the scaled items on technology, entrepreneurial and marketing skills. The questionnaire was prepared and details were collected from several weavers.

Features of the data: The aim of the study is to find the willingness of the weavers to start their own business. Were the main predictors involved in the study are future interest to market products, own business if support given, knowledge about the type of yarn, access to design facilities in their area, dyeing facilities in their area, wrapping facilities in their area, distributor in future and retailer in future. The other key features involve like demographics (age, gender, education qualification etc..)

10.1. Pilot study:

Reliability statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No of items
0.789	9

The above table shows the reliability value 0.789 obtained when all the constructs combined together and proves that the questionnaire for the data can be thus relied on for the further study. The number of features is 9.

Period of study: The time taken for the study is for about 2 months. It is a cross sectional study and the study was made at one point of time from January and February of 2020

11. Results And Discussion

11.1. Descriptive Charts:

Fig.1 Gender distribution

The fig.1 says about the number of male and female respondent of the sample. Male respondents are about

45% and female respondents are about 55% respectively.

Fig.2 Education Qualification of weavers

The fig.2 says about the education qualification of the handloom weavers. From the observation most of the peoples are below 5th standard which is about 58% approximately and average of the people are in the range of no formal education and SSLC/HSC about 28% and under graduate is about 5%

Fig.3 Product worked

The fig.3 says about the type of product that weavers work. Most of the weavers are doing cotton saree and silk saree which is about 40% and it is followed by silk saree about 38% ,other products like kora is about 25% and the least silk cotton saee is about 5%.

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Fig.4 Willingness to start own business

The fig.4 says about the willingness of the people to start the business of the weavers. Approximately 45% people are in neutral mind of starting their own business. And it is followed by the people by 28% of weavers are in the mindset of strongly disagree that they are not willing to start the business. Very a smaller number of people are agreed to start their own business which is about 14% and approximately 12% of the people are in neutral mind were only 3% of the people strongly agree to start the business.

Fig.5 Willingness to become retailer

The fig.5 gives the insights about the wavers interest to become retailer in future. approximately 43% of the people strongly disagree to become retailer in future and 25% of the weavers disagree to become retailer in future. Only 15% of the people has idea to become a retailer were 5% weavers strongly agree to become retailer in future. About 14% of the weavers are in neutral mind to become a retailer.

Fig.6 Willingness to become distributor

The fig.6 shows the weavers interest to become distributor in future. Were 40% of the weavers strongly disagree to become distributor in future. Next to that approximately 27% of the weavers are in neutral mind to become distributor in future. Then approximately 17% of the

weavers disagree to become distributor in future. Like previous figures only less than 5% of the weavers are willing to become distributor in future.

12. Multiple Regression:

Independent variable = Future interest to market products

Own business if support given Willing to start own business

Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials

Dependent variable = Being retailer in future

Hypothesis:

H0: The model is not fit Ha: The model is fit Level of confidence: 95%

Level of significance: 0.05

Table 1 Table summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.660 ^a	.436	.412	.984

This table provided the R and R² value. The R value is 0.660 which indicates positive and moderate correlation. The R² value indicates how much of independent variable can explained by the dependent variable.

The coefficient of determination R² = 0.436 The coefficient of correlation R² = 0.412

Table 2 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.350	4	17.587	18.154	.000 ^b
	Residual	91.064	94	.969		
	Total	161.414	98			

This table indicates that the regression model predicts the outcome variable significantly well. This indicates the statistical significance of the regression model that was applied. Here, p = 4.4487E-11, which is less than

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0.05, the model is fit. And indicates that, overall, the model applied can statistically significantly predict the outcome variable.

Table 3 Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	-.222	.350		-.635	.527
	Willing to invest to start own business	.400	.100	.354	3.988	.000
	Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials	.259	.083	.259	3.108	.002
	Own business if support given	.348	.089	.347	3.889	.000
	Future interest to market products	-.091	.085	-.094	-1.066	.289

The table below, Coefficients, provides us with information on each predictor variable. This gives us the information we need to interest to become retailer in future from Future interest to market products, Own business if support given, Willing to invest to start own business and having sufficient contact to produce raw materials. Willingness to start own business has more effect on the deciding being retailer in future. By looking at the B column under the Unstandardized Coefficients column, we can present the regression equation as:

Willingness to become retailer in future = $-0.222 + (0.400) * \text{Willing to invest} + (0.256) * \text{Contact to produce raw materials} + (0.348) * \text{Own business if support given} + (-0.091) * \text{Future interest to market products}$

13. Correlation

Hypothesis:

H₀: there is no significant correlation between knowledge in the type of yarn and having sufficient contact to produce raw material

H_a: there is significant correlation between knowledge in the type of yarn and having sufficient contact to produce raw material

Level of confidence: 95% Level of significance: 0.05

Table 4 Correlations

		Knowledge in type of yarns	Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials
Knowledge in type of yarns	Pearson Correlation	1	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials	Pearson Correlation	.562**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

From the above table the $p = 1.2148E-9$ which is less than 0.05. so, there is significant correlation between knowledge in the type of yarn and having sufficient contact to produce raw material. The Pearson correlation value is 0.562 which is positive and high correlation.

14.Independent Sample T Test

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant difference between male and female of having contact to produce raw material

Ha: There is significant difference between male and female of having contact to produce rawmaterial

Level of confidence: 95% Level of significance: 0.05

Table 5 Group Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials	male	48	2.83	1.294	.187
	female	52	2.08	1.152	.160

From the above table, mean of male is 2.83 and the male of female is 2.08. there is slight difference in the mean value between male and female

Table 6 Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Having sufficient contact to produce raw materials	Equal variances assumed	1.104	.296	3.092	98	.003	.756	.245	.271	1.242
	Equal variances not assumed			3.078	94.385	.003	.756	.246	.268	1.244

The significance value is 0.03 which is less than 0.05. There is significant difference between male and female of having contact to produce raw material. So, the contact to produce raw material between male and female will differ.

15. Analysis Of Variance

Hypothesis:

H0: There is a homogeneity exist among the weaver's willingness to start own business across different education qualification

Ha: There is no homogeneity exist among the weaver's willingness to start own business across different education qualification

Level of confidence: 95% Level of significance: 0.05

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Table 7 Descriptives

Willing to invest to start own business								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					LowerBound	UpperBound		
no formal education	18	2.11	1.079	.254	1.57	2.65	1	4
below 5th standard	58	2.41	1.109	.146	2.12	2.71	1	5
SSLC/HSC	18	3.11	1.183	.279	2.52	3.70	1	5
under graduate	6	3.00	.632	.258	2.34	3.66	2	4
Total	100	2.52	1.132	.113	2.30	2.74	1	5

The average mean perception score for different education qualification of weavers varies from

2.52 to 3.11 which can be seen from the summary table. SSLC/HSC qualification of weavers has the highest mean score of 3.11 followed by the undergraduate qualification with mean of 3.00

Table 8 ANOVA

Willing to invest to start own business					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	11.335	3	3.778	3.137	.029
Within Groups	115.625	96	1.204		
Total	126.960	99			

ANOVA results indicate the value to be 3.137 and the p value is found to be 0.029 which is lesser than 0.05. as the p value is lesser than 0.05, it can be decided to accept the alternate hypothesis. Which further implies there is no homogeneity exist among the weaver's willingness to start own business across different education qualification.

Table 9 Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: willing to invest to start own business						
Tukey HSD						
(I) Educationqualification	(J) Education qualification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					LowerBound	UpperBound
no formal education	below 5th standard	-.303	.296	.737	-1.08	.47
	SSLC/HSC	-1.000*	.366	.037	-1.96	-.04
	under graduate	-.889	.517	.320	-2.24	.46
below 5th standard	no formal education	.303	.296	.737	-.47	1.08
	SSLC/HSC	-.697	.296	.093	-1.47	.08
	under graduate	-.586	.471	.600	-1.82	.64
SSLC/HSC	no formal education	1.000*	.366	.037	.04	1.96
	below 5th standard	.697	.296	.093	-.08	1.47
	under graduate	.111	.517	.996	-1.24	1.46
under graduate	no formal education	.889	.517	.320	-.46	2.24
	below 5th standard	.586	.471	.600	-.64	1.82
	SSLC/HSC	-.111	.517	.996	-1.46	1.24

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The results of turkey (multiple comparison table) indicates the presence of significant differences between

different education qualification of the weavers. From the table SSLC/HSC obtained the highest score among all other qualification.

16.Exploratory Data Analysis

Table 10 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.750
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	217.892
	Df	21
	Sig.	.000

This is the measure of sampling Adequacy. The cut off measure to report that the sample is adequate is KMO measure > or = 0.50. Here the KMO Measure = 0.750 and so sample is adequate

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: The hypothesis for BTS is $H_0 : r = 0$

$H_a : r \neq 0$

The test reveals the significance. If $p < 0.05$, then the test is significant . The test assures that there is significant correlation among the variables.

Table 11 Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Future interest to market products	1.000	.555
Own business if support given	1.000	.710
Being retailer in future	1.000	.696
Distributor in future	1.000	.672
Access to design facilities in their area	1.000	.533
Willing to invest to start own business	1.000	.557
Knowledge in type of yarns	1.000	.638

From the communalities table, we can identify the adequate representation of the variables- based extraction value, which ideally should be greater than 0.5. The greater the values, means more adequate representation. From the communalities table given above it is evident that all the extraction of all the variables are equal or more than 0.5. So, all the variables have an adequate representation in the factor.

Table 12 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.153	45.050	45.050	3.153	45.050	45.050	2.618	37.403	37.403
2	1.207	17.250	62.300	1.207	17.250	62.300	1.743	24.896	62.300
3	.848	12.119	74.418						
4	.621	8.866	83.285						
5	.507	7.249	90.534						
6	.424	6.057	96.591						
7	.239	3.409	100.000						

From the above Total Variance Table, it is evident that two factors are extracted and 62.3 percent of the total variance is explained by all these two factors. The first two components have Eigen values greater than 1. The eigenvalue is a measure of how much of the variance of the observed variables a factor explains. Any factor with an eigenvalue ≥ 1 explains more variance than a single observed variable. Eigen values are the sum of the factor loadings and its value greater than 1, signifies the contribution of the variables to the factor.

Scree Plot: There is a (deep) sudden steep after 2 factors. The scree plot also confirms the same as given by the total variance explained table. The scree plot is a graph of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain.

Fig.7 Scree plot of exploratory data analysis

Table 13 Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Future interest to market products	.486	.564
Own business if support given	.599	.593
Being retailer in future	.830	-.085
Distributor in future	.817	-.072
Access to design facilities in their area	.683	-.258
Willing to invest to start own business	.745	-.048
-Knowledge in type of yarns	.426	-.675

The factor loadings that explains the correlation between the variable and factor is given by this Component Matrix. “future interest to market products”, and “knowledge in type of yarns” has loaded on component 2. Similarly, v2, v3, v4 and v5 have loaded on component 1. This situation calls for rotation of the axis. So, varimax rotation can be performed to bring more clarity on the factor loading.

Table 14 Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Future interest to market products	.118	.735
Own business if support given	.199	.819
Being retailer in future	.751	.363
Distributor in future	.733	.367
Access to design facilities in their area	.717	.138
Willing to invest to start own business	.659	.349
Knowledge in type of yarns	.717	-.351

The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. Rotation does not actually change anything but makes the interpretation of the analysis easier. V1, V2 are loaded in component 1 and v3, v4, v5, v6 and v7 are loaded in component 2.

Component 1:

- Future interest to market products
- Own business if support given

Component 2:

- Being retailer in future
- Distributor in future
- Access to design facilities in their area
- Willing to invest to start own business
- Knowledge in type of yarns

Based on the variable grouping with the components, the components can be named now.

DESISION TO START BUSINESS
Future interest to market products
Own business if support given

FACTORS TO START BUSINESS
Being retailer in future
Distributor in future
Access to design facilities in their area
Willing to invest to start own business
Knowledge in type of yarns

17.Findings, Business Implication And Conclusion Findings:

Results reveal that the handloom saree weavers fall in the low income group and the people involved in weaving are above the age of 50. The millennials are not interested in involving handloom weaving where the

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upcoming generation of the weaver's family are not

interested to making their children in involve in weaving due to low wages and their family background. So, from the analysis we have concluded that the weavers have sufficient knowledge about the raw materials and weaving they are not interested to invest and start own business or to become as a distributor or retailer in future. They have no education qualification and rather than weaving they are not involved in other professions. Even though they do weaving as a regular occupation they are not able to produce more sarees and the earnings from the product is low. So, they are not willing to start own business.

18. Discussion:

Most of the weavers in district fall in low income group and they need some support to start the business. Even though support is given most of the people are not interested in investing in own business. Their willingness can be increased by getting loans and using ideas like,

- Build and expand base by identifying target buyers and approaching new buyers
- In effect create channels and platforms for brand expansion and reach
- Creating relevant tactical and strategic partnership and collaborations with like minded businesses for synergy as well as developing and expanding a data base of home textile influences like others (interior decorators, etc)

19. Conclusion:

From all the analysis and survey the conclusion is that the weavers are not interest to start the own business as they don't have enough background to maintain the business and due to the development of power loom sectors, they feel that the profit earn from the handloom weaving was very low. So, as a result the weavers in Coimbatore district are not interested to start own business.

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